

1 **Urban environment during pregnancy and lung function, wheezing, and asthma**
2 **in school-age children. The Generation R Study.**

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68 **ABSTRACT**

69 The urban environment during pregnancy may influence child's respiratory health, but
70 scarce evidence exists on systematic evaluation of multiple urban exposures (e.g., air
71 pollution, natural spaces, noise, built environment) on children's lung function, wheezing, and
72 asthma development.

73 We aimed to examine the association of the urban environment during pregnancy
74 with lung function, preschool wheezing, and school-age asthma.

75 We included 5,624 mother-child pairs participating in a population-based prospective
76 birth cohort. We estimated 30 urban environmental exposures including air pollution, road
77 traffic noise, traffic, green spaces, blue spaces, and built environment during pregnancy. At
78 10 years of age, lung function was measured by spirometry. Information on preschool
79 wheezing and physician-diagnosed school-age asthma was obtained from multiple
80 questionnaires. We described single-exposure associations with respiratory outcomes using
81 an exposome-wide association study. We also identified patterns of urban exposures with
82 hierarchical clustering on principal components analysis and examined their associations
83 with respiratory outcomes using multivariate regression models.

84 Single-exposure analyses showed associations of higher particulate matter (PM) with
85 lower mid-expiratory flow ($FEF_{25-75\%}$) (e.g., for $PM_{<2.5}$ μm of diameter [$PM_{2.5}$] z-score=-0.06
86 [-0.09, -0.03]) and higher forced expiratory volume in 1s (FEV1) and forced vital capacity
87 (FVC) (e.g., for $PM_{2.5}$ FEV_1 0.05 [0.02, 0.08]) after correction for multiple-hypothesis testing.
88 Cluster analysis described three patterns of urban exposures during pregnancy and showed
89 that the cluster characterized by higher levels of air pollution, noise, walkability, street
90 connectivity, and lower levels of natural spaces were associated with lower $FEF_{25-75\%}$ (-0.08 [-
91 0.17, 0.00]), and higher odds of preschool wheezing (1.21 [1.03, 1.43]).

92 This study shows that the characteristics of the urban environment during pregnancy
93 are of relevance to the offspring's respiratory health during childhood.

94

95 **INTRODUCTION**

96 Lung function and asthma development during childhood are key determinants for respiratory
97 health into adult life (1). Early life, particularly the pregnancy period, is a critical stage of
98 development that is especially vulnerable to environmental exposures. Exposures occurring
99 in that period may have long-term health implications (2,3). Many early life environmental
100 exposures are associated with the development of lower lung function and risk of asthma in
101 childhood (4-25). Air pollution exposure after birth is suggested to be associated with lower
102 lung function (4), increased risk of wheezing and asthma (5-7), and exacerbating both pre-
103 existing conditions (8) during childhood. Previous studies examining the role of maternal
104 exposure to air pollution during pregnancy on child's respiratory health reported mixed
105 findings (7,9,18-21,10-17). Some studies found that maternal exposure to air pollution
106 during pregnancy was associated with lower lung function (9-14), and increased risk of
107 wheezing (15) and asthma in children (15-18), while others did not (7,14,19-21). The
108 potential adverse health effects of other exposures related to the urban environment such as
109 noise (21,22), lack of green (21,23) and blue spaces (21,24), increased built environment
110 (21), and especially the concurrence of these exposures (21) on respiratory health is limited
111 and inconsistent (25). Only one previous study has assessed maternal exposure to an
112 extensive number of exposures related to the urban environment (i.e., air pollution, natural
113 spaces, noise, built environment, traffic) during pregnancy and observed no association with
114 child's lung function but did not study wheezing or asthma as outcomes (21). Evaluating the
115 impact of the urban environment on respiratory health is essential as half of the global
116 population is currently living in urban settings, and this proportion is expected to increase up
117 to 70% by 2050 (26). Despite that urban living offers opportunities for a healthy living
118 including access to services and goods, employment and social interaction, it may also imply
119 increasing exposure to a harmful environment (27). Exploring the urban environment as a
120 whole in relation to respiratory health, especially in vulnerable developing periods of life, may
121 help to identify harmful urban environments to ultimately identify effective prevention
122 strategies to reduce them. We hypothesised that the urban environment during pregnancy

123 may play a role in the development of the respiratory and immune systems that may affect
124 respiratory health during childhood, Therefore, we aimed to examine the associations of
125 exposure to the urban environment during pregnancy, including air pollution, noise, traffic,
126 green and blue spaces, and built environment with lung function, preschool wheezing, and
127 school-age asthma among 5,624 children participating in a population-based prospective
128 cohort study.

129

130 **METHODS**

131 **Design** The present study was embedded in the Generation R Study, a population-based
132 prospective birth cohort study in Rotterdam, the Netherlands. Pregnant women were
133 recruited during pregnancy at their health care centers between 2002 and 2006 (28). The
134 study was approved by the Medical Ethical Committee of the Erasmus MC, University
135 Medical Centre in Rotterdam. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. A
136 total of 5,624 mother-child pairs were included in the current study (Figure S1).

137

138 **Urban environment during pregnancy** The range of urban environment variables was
139 estimated at the home address during pregnancy using geographic information systems
140 (GIS) modelling. We included a total of 30 exposures from the following exposure groups: air
141 pollution (n=11), road traffic noise (n=2), traffic (n=1), green spaces (n=5), blue spaces (n=2),
142 and built environment (n=9) (Table 1). Complete details on the exposures assessed,
143 distributions, and data sources for the estimations are fully described in Supplementary
144 Table S1 and Pearson correlations between all exposures in Figure S2.

145

146 **Child's respiratory outcomes** Lung function was measured at a mean age of 9.79 years
147 (standard deviation (SD): 0.35 years) by spirometry following the American Thoracic Society
148 and European Respiratory Society guidelines (29). We measured forced expiratory volume in
149 1s (FEV₁), forced vital capacity (FVC), FEV₁/FVC, and mid-expiratory flow (FEF_{25-75%}) and
150 converted these into age-, height-, sex-, and ethnicity-adjusted z-scores (30). Z-scores

151 indicate the change in standard deviations a measured value is from the predicted according
152 to age, height, sex, and ethnicity (31). Children with ≥ 1 acceptable manoeuvre were included
153 in the analyses. Preschool wheezing and school-age asthma were assessed from parental-
154 reported questionnaires adapted from the International Study on Asthma and Allergy in
155 Childhood (ISAAC) (32). Preschool wheezing was assessed from having had any wheezing
156 from birth until the age of 5 years. This was assessed from a question of having had
157 wheezing in the past 12 months (yes, no), which was annually asked at the ages of 1 to 5
158 years. At a mean age of 9.79 years, school asthma was defined as ever-physician-diagnosed
159 asthma with either wheezing or asthma medication use in the past 12 months.

160

161 **Covariates** Maternal characteristics were obtained from questionnaires during pregnancy
162 and included highest educational level finished (low: no education, primary school,
163 secondary school or intermediate vocational training; high: university degree or higher
164 vocational training), age at pregnancy (years), pre-pregnancy body mass index (BMI; kg/m²),
165 smoking during pregnancy (yes;no), and history of asthma and atopy (ever been diagnosed,
166 yes;no). Additionally, information on area-level SES was obtained from the Social and
167 Cultural Planning Office of The Netherlands. Area-level SES was assessed as quintiles of
168 the neighbourhood deprivation, considering education, income, and position on the labour
169 market of the neighbourhood inhabitants. Child's sex (female; male), gestational age at birth
170 (weeks), and birth weight (g) information was collected from midwife and hospital records at
171 birth. Child's height (cm) was measured at the time of the lung function assessment and
172 ethnicity information (caucasian, african/american, south east asian, north east asian,
173 other/mixed) was assessed by country of birth from parents and grandparents from
174 questionnaires. Covariates were selected from literature and summarised in a directed
175 acyclic graph (DAG) to depict the known and hypothesised causal relations between
176 variables and avoid adjusting for mediators or colliders (Figure S3).

177

178 **Statistical analysis** We performed a non-response analysis comparing mothers and
179 children included in the analyses to those lost to follow up at the age of 10 years using chi-
180 square tests for categorical variables and independent samples t-tests for continuous
181 variables. Multiple imputation by chained equations (33) was performed for missing values in
182 exposures and selected covariates. All variables not following a normal distribution were
183 transformed to approach normality. A total of 10 imputed datasets were generated and
184 Rubin's rules were applied to summarise effect estimates (33). We standardised by the
185 interquartile range (IQR) of all continuous exposures to ensure comparability of exposure
186 estimates. Therefore, all continuous exposure estimates are expressed as IQR increase
187 (equivalent to passing from the 25th to the 75th percentile). Because area-level SES may play
188 a substantial role in the association between the urban environment and childhood
189 respiratory outcomes, we standardised all exposures by the mean exposure level in each
190 quintile of area-level SES to reduce any residual confounding.

191 We examined associations of the urban environment during pregnancy with lung function,
192 preschool wheezing, and school-age asthma using two complementary approaches. As a
193 first exploratory analysis, we performed a descriptive screening of single exposure-outcome
194 associations with an exposome-wide association study (ExWAS). The ExWAS assessed the
195 associations through multivariable linear (for lung function) or logistic (for wheezing and
196 asthma) regression models and was corrected for multiple testing using an adapted version
197 of the Bonferroni correction that takes into account the correlation structure of the data
198 (corrected p-value=0.003) (34). Estimates for lung function models are expressed as z-score
199 change and for wheeze and asthma models as odds ratio (OR). Second, to assess the
200 associations closer to a real-life scenario because populations are simultaneously exposed
201 to numerous urban environmental exposures, we applied a hierarchical clustering on
202 principal components (HCPC) analysis to identify children sharing similar urban exposure
203 patterns. This was considered the main analysis. We first applied a principal component
204 analysis (PCA) to reduce the data dimension and retained the components that explained at
205 least 90% of the variance (Table S2). We applied an ascending hierarchical classification

206 based on the PCA components to identify clusters of exposure (Figure S4). Then we used
207 the identified clusters as the independent variable in the linear and logistic regression
208 models. Models from both approaches were adjusted for a common set of covariates
209 selected from the DAG (Figure S3). Lung function models were adjusted for maternal
210 education, pre-pregnancy BMI, age, smoking during pregnancy, history of asthma or atopy,
211 and child's ethnicity and season of birth. Wheezing and asthma models were additionally
212 adjusted for child's sex.

213 Further sensitivity analyses were performed to assess the robustness of the results. We
214 described the levels of urban exposures and distribution of outcomes in each area-level SES
215 strata. Lung function models were repeated including only children with 3 acceptable and
216 reproducible manoeuvres from the spirometry test. We further repeated the cluster analyses
217 excluding children born preterm or with a low birth weight, assessing preschool wheezing
218 considering wheeze presenting at only 1 or at 2 or more ages from age 1 to 5 years, and
219 assessing wheezing separately at every age from age 1 to 5 years. Statistical analyses were
220 performed using R Statistical Software version 3.6.1.

221

222 **RESULTS**

223 **Subject characteristics** Maternal and child characteristics are shown in Table 2. Maternal
224 exposures are shown in Table S1. Briefly, median (IQR) pregnancy air pollution levels (e.g.,
225 $\text{NO}_2=38.48$ (7.48) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, $\text{PM}_{2.5}= 19.72$ (3.83) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) were above the 2021 WHO air quality
226 guidelines (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for NO_2 , 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$). Of all mothers, 52% were exposed to daily
227 road traffic noise levels above the current WHO recommendations ($\text{Lden}>53$ dB). Non-
228 response analyses showed that children included in the analyses had mothers who were
229 older, with lower pre-pregnancy BMI, higher education, and living in less deprived
230 neighbourhoods compared to those lost at follow up at the age of 10 years. Children included
231 in the analyses were less likely to be born preterm or with a low birth weight and were less
232 ethnically diverse (Table S3). There were no differences in maternal and child characteristics
233 between the complete case and the imputed datasets (Table S4).

234

235 **Urban environment during pregnancy and child's respiratory outcomes**

236 **Single exposure analyses** Higher exposure to PM was related to higher FEV₁ (z-score
237 change for PM_{2.5}: 0.05 [0.02, 0.08], PM₁₀: 0.04 [0.01, 0.07]; PM_{coarse}: 0.04 [0.01, 0.07]) and
238 FVC (PM_{2.5}: 0.06 [0.03, 0.08], PM₁₀: 0.05 [0.02, 0.08]; PM_{coarse}: 0.04 [0.01, 0.07]), and lower
239 FEF_{25-75%} (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀: -0.06 [-0.09, -0.03], PM_{2.5abs}: -0.03 [-0.07, 0.00]; PM_{coarse}: -0.03 [-
240 0.06, 0.00]) (Table S5). Higher exposure to NO₂ was associated with lower FEF_{25-75%} (-0.04 [-
241 0.07, 0.00]) (Table S5), and nitrogen oxides with higher odds of preschool wheeze (OR for
242 NO₂ and NO_x: 1.08 [1.01, 1.16]) (Table S6). Higher size of the nearest major blue space was
243 associated with higher FEV₁ (0.04 [0.01, 0.06]) and FVC (0.03 [0.00, 0.05]), and lower odds
244 of school-age asthma (0.87 [0.75, 0.99]). Indicators of urbanicity (i.e., exposures from the
245 built environment) were associated with lower lung function and higher odds of preschool
246 wheezing (e.g., street connectivity with lower FEV₁ [-0.03 (-0.06, 0.00)], and facilities density
247 (e.g., schools, medical centres, shops) with higher wheezing [1.07 (1.01, 1.14)]; Table S5-
248 S6). However, after correction for multiple testing (p=0.003), only the associations of higher
249 PM_{2.5} with higher FEV₁, FVC and lower FEF_{25-75%}, higher PM₁₀ with higher FVC and lower
250 FEF_{25-75%}, and higher PM_{coarse} with higher FVC remained statistically significant.

251

252 **Cluster analyses** We obtained 3 different clusters of the urban environment (Figure 1).
253 Cluster 1 (n=1,598;) identified mother-child pairs exposed to lower levels of air pollution, road
254 traffic noise, traffic, and urbanisation, in terms of population density, building density, and
255 walkability, and to higher levels of green and blue spaces. We selected this cluster as the
256 reference cluster in our analyses because it had the lowest levels of a priori harmful
257 exposures. Cluster 2 (n=2,835) was characterized by lower levels of air pollutants and noise,
258 higher distance to natural spaces, more densely population and built areas, and less diversity
259 in land use. Cluster 3 (n=1,191) identified mother-child pairs who were exposed to higher air
260 pollution and noise, and lived in more walkable areas, with lower exposure to green and blue
261 spaces. Mother-child pairs between clusters differed in terms of maternal age, pre-pregnancy

262 BMI, education, and child season of birth, ethnicity, and rates of preschool wheezing (Table
263 S7). Most prominently, compared to Cluster 1, children belonging to Cluster 3 had lower
264 $FEF_{25-75\%}$ (-0.08 [-0.17, 0.00]) and higher odds of preschool wheezing (1.21 [1.03, 1.43]). We
265 did not observe associations of Cluster 3 with FEV_1 , FVC, FEV_1/FVC nor with school-age
266 asthma and neither of Cluster 2 with any respiratory outcome (Table 3).

267

268 **Sensitivity analyses** We observed differences in the distributions of exposures across SES
269 strata without a clear pattern of harmful or beneficial exposures across quintiles of SES
270 (Table S8). The observed associations remained materially similar when we included only
271 children with reproducible spirometry measurements (Table S9-S10), and when excluding
272 preterm and low weight born children (Table S11). The observed effect estimates for the
273 associations of urban exposure clusters with preschool wheezing were similar when
274 assessing wheezing presenting at only 1 age or at ≥ 2 ages from age 1 to 5 years as the
275 outcomes. We did not observe associations at any specific age separately although a
276 tendency for higher odds for associations of urban exposure clusters with preschool
277 wheezing at age 2 years was observed (Table S12).

278

279 **DISCUSSION**

280 This study is one of the first that systematically analysed multiple urban exposures in relation
281 to child's respiratory health and described three patterns of urban exposures during
282 pregnancy in an urban setting in The Netherlands. This study showed that higher exposure
283 to particulate matter during pregnancy was associated with lower lung function in mid-to-
284 small airways. This study also showed that living during pregnancy in an urban environment
285 characterised by higher levels of air pollution, noise, walkability, street connectivity, and
286 lower levels of natural spaces contributes to lower lung function in mid-to-small airways, and
287 to increased odds of preschool wheezing.

288

289 **Comparison with previous studies**

290 We considered a wide range of urban exposures to create clusters of exposures and we
291 observed that compared to mother-child pairs living in less polluted, less noisy, more natural,
292 and less urban areas, those living in more walkable areas with higher air pollution and noise,
293 and lower levels of green and blue spaces had lower $FEF_{25-75\%}$ and increased odds of
294 preschool wheezing. We did not observe notable associations with those living in areas with
295 lower levels of air pollution, noise, natural spaces, and higher levels of urbanization with
296 respiratory outcomes. This suggests that lower levels of air pollution alone might not be
297 enough and highlights the importance of the existence of urban settings that are
298 characterised by lower traffic-related air pollution, lower urbanisation (i.e., lower building and
299 population density or street connectivity), and higher volume of areas with natural spaces
300 simultaneously for a better respiratory health of children. To our knowledge, only one study
301 had previously considered a wide range of urban exposures during pregnancy in relation to
302 lung function (21), but not with wheezing and asthma in childhood. In that study, authors did
303 not find any association with lung function in single or multiple-exposure analysis. They only
304 reported a positive association with inverse distance to the nearest road, considered a
305 spurious finding. In that study, the statistical power was limited to assess the multiplicity of
306 the exposures included with the small effect on lung function that was expected. Differences
307 in findings with our study might also be explained by non-differential exposure
308 misclassification due to measurement error that might have attenuated the effect estimates
309 (21).

310 Most previous studies used single-exposure approaches that do not account for the complex
311 interrelationship of the multiple environmental exposures that are present in an urban setting.
312 Our results from the single-exposure analysis confirm the adverse effects of air pollution on
313 mid-to-small airways (9,11,13), and on the risk of early childhood wheezing (15,35) observed
314 in previous studies and in our findings in cluster analysis. However, in single-exposure
315 analyses we observed an association of higher prenatal exposure to particulate matter with
316 higher FEV_1 and FVC, which was not present in the cluster analysis. These contradictory
317 results add to the current inconsistent evidence (9,10,12,14,19–21), highlight the importance

318 of considering air pollution within the complexity of urban exposures and should be further
319 explored before any strong conclusions can be made. Of importance, our findings highlight
320 the relevance of FEF_{25-75%} as an early marker of small airways impairment (36).

321 Previous studies that assessed noise exposure during pregnancy reported null associations
322 in relation to wheezing and asthma until adolescence. Considering the prevalent high noise
323 exposure and our findings, early life exposure to noise in relation to child's respiratory health
324 merits further investigation. Living in less natural (green and blue) areas was detrimental for
325 children's lung health. In line with our results, the scarce available evidence shows a
326 potential beneficial effect of green spaces (23). Our study is the first to report an association
327 between blue spaces and respiratory health, observed in cluster and single-exposure
328 analyses. Only one study previously assessed prenatal exposure to blue spaces in relation to
329 lung function and reported null associations (21). However, the levels of blue spaces in that
330 study were very low and were only assessed as presence or absence of blue spaces in a
331 300 m buffer (21). The Rotterdam area is a unique setting with very high proportion of blue
332 spaces (including a river, lakes, canals, and an extensive industrial port), compared to other
333 cities. Given the potential health benefits of blue spaces, but at the same time the risks of the
334 industrial port, further research is guaranteed. We observed that a built environment with
335 higher street connectivity, facilities, and walkability, when assessed in combination with other
336 urban exposures, was related to worse respiratory health. Contrary to the only study that has
337 assessed the influence of the built environment during pregnancy on childhood respiratory
338 health so far (21), which reported no associations with lung function.

339 Every urban environment is unique in terms of its urban features and demographic
340 characteristics, thus, our results need to be interpreted in view of its specific urban setting.
341 Rotterdam, with an extension of 324 km², is the second largest city in the Netherlands with
342 663,900 inhabitants and one of the most densely populated in the country with 3040
343 inhabitants/km² as of 2023 (37). It comprises a large number of green and blue spaces as
344 well as an extensive cycling network, including a length of 117 km of cycling network per 100
345 km of motorway (38). In socioeconomic terms based on the city's mean levels of prosperity,

346 education, and employment, Rotterdam ranks among the lowest in The Netherlands (39).
347 Higher socioeconomic deprivation has been consistently associated with worse health
348 outcomes (40). However, the way how SES influences the associations of urban exposures
349 with health is not clear, it can be non-linear, and is context specific (41). Similarly, the
350 association between socioeconomic deprivation and patterns of urban exposures is unclear
351 and context specific. While in the US studies have shown an association of higher
352 deprivation with exposure to more harmful environments, in the EU findings have been mixed
353 (42). In our study population, levels of exposure across SES quintiles were mixed. Because
354 of that, we thoughtfully adjusted our models for the relevant individual-level SES covariates
355 and we further standardised the exposures by area-level SES. Given the complexity and
356 uniqueness of urban scenarios in terms of the coexistence of potentially beneficial and
357 detrimental exposures, more studies integrating many urban exposures in the context of
358 socioeconomic factors in different urban settings are needed.

359

360 **Interpretation of results**

361 Our study is based on the Developmental Origins of Health and Disease (DOHaD)
362 hypothesis, which posits that exposures during critical periods of development, particularly
363 during pregnancy, can influence long-term health outcomes (2). During pregnancy, the lungs
364 undergo crucial phases of formation and development and are especially vulnerable to
365 environmental exposures (3). Exposures during pregnancy may lead to adaptations and
366 alterations in the development that could manifest as long-term health effects, as in
367 alterations in lung function or manifestations of wheeze and asthma symptoms during
368 childhood.

369 In our study we observed that living during pregnancy in an urban environment characterised
370 by higher levels of air pollution, noise, walkability, street connectivity, and lower levels of
371 natural spaces contributes to a lower lung function in mid-to-small airways, and to higher
372 odds of preschool wheezing, but not with school age asthma. Preschool wheezing is a
373 respiratory symptom that may also represent a different aetiology than childhood asthma.

374 Preschool wheezing may be triggered by a myriad of factors, including viral infections, which
375 are prevalent in this younger age group. Repeated wheezing episodes before the age of 5
376 may not necessarily progress to a persistent asthma phenotype, which is consistent with the
377 lack of associations observed with school-age asthma. The urban environment during
378 pregnancy may alter the development of the immune system making younger children more
379 susceptible to respiratory infections.

380 Air pollutants inhaled by the mother during pregnancy can cross the placenta and thus have
381 a direct effect on the foetus development (43). Oxidative stress, inflammation, and epigenetic
382 changes are suspected to play an important role on the respiratory effects of air pollution
383 (12,44) as well as disrupting the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis (45). Early life air
384 pollution exposure has been linked to lower club cell secretory protein (CC16) levels in
385 childhood, which in turn is associated with decreased lung function (46,47). Air pollution
386 could directly affect lung development by disturbing organogenesis due to the
387 aforementioned mechanisms, and indirectly affect it through adverse birth outcomes.

388 Noise acts as a physiological and psychological stressor. It is suggested to promote stress
389 responses through the HPA axis leading to the release of stress hormones such as cortisol
390 (48). Maternal psychological distress during pregnancy has been associated with preschool
391 wheezing (49), and lower lung function and asthma at school-age (50). Stress mechanisms
392 may also disrupt sleep and night-time recovery of the immune system, leading to
393 inflammatory processes also in the respiratory system (48). Further, chronic stress-reactions
394 and sleep disturbances may lead to alterations in the endocrine system that could impair
395 critical developmental processes of the lung and immune system (48,51). Green and blue
396 spaces could act as mitigators of harmful exposures such as air pollution (52). Exposure to
397 green spaces around the home has been associated with reduced serum IgE levels in
398 children, which is a biomarker of asthma and bronchial hyperresponsiveness (53). Also, they
399 could have a beneficial effect by promoting healthier lifestyles, reducing stress (e.g.,
400 increasing physical activity, promoting social cohesion) (54), or by influencing individual's
401 microbiome as postulated by the biodiversity hypothesis (55). The features of the built

402 environment can influence on the magnitude of environmental stressors and on health-
403 related behaviors (56). Although in The Netherlands the use of active transportation (i.e.,
404 cycling) is common, more efforts can be put into developing an even more pedestrian or
405 active transportation focused and naturalized design in detriment of traffic. That would lead to
406 less traffic-related air pollution and increased physical activity in the population, that
407 consequently would provide beneficial health effects.

408

409 **Strengths and limitations**

410 The strengths of this study are its population-based design with a large sample size and its
411 assessment with complementary approaches to assess the complexity of a wide range of
412 urban environment exposures in relation to multiple outcomes across childhood. This might
413 help avoid publication bias compared to single-exposure approaches. To our knowledge, this
414 is the first study to comprehensively assess a wide range of urban environment exposures
415 on wheeze and asthma in addition to lung function outcomes in children. We used the HCPC
416 method for multiple exposure assessment, which allowed us to identify patterns of urban
417 exposures by reducing the dimensionality while dealing with the correlation structure of the
418 exposure dataset, facilitated the interpretation of the urban exposures and respiratory health
419 outcomes, and reduced the problem of multiple testing (57). However, we acknowledge there
420 are other multiple-exposure assessment approaches such as variable selection and
421 dimension reduction methods (57,58). Also, we acknowledge that the identified patterns of
422 exposure are study area specific, which merits future validation of our results in other urban
423 settings. Further, lung function was assessed with spirometry following the ATS/ERS
424 guidelines and performed by trained research staff, which provided objective and reliable
425 measurements. Some methodological limitations need to be addressed. First, results for
426 $FEF_{25-75\%}$ need to be interpreted with caution as it is a parameter with high variability,
427 especially in children. However, in sensitivity analyses, when we included only children with
428 reproducible spirometries, results remained robust. Second, in approaches examining a
429 broad range of exposures, measurement error bias is present in a different magnitude across

430 exposures. Thus, the comparison of each exposure associations with respiratory health
431 should be interpreted cautiously. Third, although we examined exposure-by-exposure
432 associations as well as simultaneous exposures identifying patterns of exposures in the
433 cluster analysis in an attempt to get closer to a real-life scenario, we did not assess possible
434 effect modification nor mediation between co-occurring exposures because the complete
435 interrelationship between all co-occurring exposures in an urban environment is not yet fully
436 understood and there is yet no consensus on the best methodological approach. Last, we
437 focused our study to exposures occurring during pregnancy because of the relevance and
438 potential long-term health implications of exposures occurring in that period. However, we did
439 not add exposures occurring during childhood to prevent more layers of complexity into the
440 already highly advanced models leading to difficulties in interpretation of findings.
441 Nevertheless, we consider childhood also as a relevant period of development and
442 exposures occurring during such period could have important implications and potential to
443 modify health effects initiated during prenatal development. Further studies are needed to
444 address the complexity of cumulative prenatal and childhood exposures to carefully explore
445 individual effects in critical age windows, which would hold significant public health
446 implications for the development of mitigation strategies tailored to specific life stages.

447

448 **CONCLUSION**

449 In conclusion, this study shows that the urban environment during pregnancy is of relevance
450 to the offspring's respiratory health in childhood. Thus, improving the urban design to
451 minimise harmful and maximise beneficial urban exposures, along with reducing social
452 inequalities related, is key to ensure a healthy respiratory development in childhood, that in
453 turn, will result in a reduction of respiratory morbidity later in life.

454

455 **TABLES AND FIGURES**

456 **Table 1.** Summary of urban environmental exposures

457

Exposure family	Exposure
Air pollution	NO ₂ , NO _x , PM ₁₀ , PM _{2.5} , PM _{2.5} absorbance, PM _{coarse} , PM _{2.5} elemental components (Cu, Fe, K, Si, Zn)
Noise	Lden, Ln
Traffic	Inverse distance to the nearest road
Green spaces	NDVI (within 100m, 300m, 500m buffer), size of nearest major green space (>5000 m ²), distance to the nearest major green space (>5000 m ²)
Blue spaces	Size of the nearest major blue space (>5000 m ²), distance to the nearest major blue space (>5000 m ²)
Built environment	Population density, building density (within 100m, 300m, 500m buffer), street connectivity within 300m buffer, facilities density within 300m buffer, facilities richness within 300m buffer, Land Use Mix (Shannon's Evenness Index) within 300m buffer, Walkability within 300m buffer

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*Estimated using geographic information system within PostgreSQL (copyright © 1996-2017 The PostgreSQL Global Development Group), PostGIS (Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 License <http://postgis.net>), Python (Python Software Foundation. Python Language Reference, version 2.7. Available at <http://www.python.org>) and R (R Core Team (2013). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL <http://www.R-project.org/>) platforms.

467 **Table 2.** Maternal and child characteristics.
 468

	Population for analysis (n=5,624)
Maternal characteristics	
Age (years)	31.00 (4.92)
Pre-pregnancy BMI (kg/m ²)	23.47 (4.10)
Education, low	2550 (49%)
Smoking	
Never	3784 (77%)
Before pregnancy	429 (9%)
During pregnancy	727 (15%)
History of asthma or atopy, yes,	1804 (37%)
Area-level SES	
Quintile 1, least deprived	593 (11%)
Quintile 2	646 (12%)
Quintile 3	663 (12%)
Quintile 4	616 (11%)
Quintile 5, most deprived	3087 (55%)
Child characteristics	
Sex, female	2822 (50%)
Gestational age at birth (weeks)	40.14 (1.86)
Preterm birth (<37 weeks)	260 (5%)
Birth weight (g)	3450.00 (690.00)
Low birth weight (<2500 g)	239 (4%)
Season of birth	
Spring	1333 (24%)
Summer	1516 (27%)
Autumn	1541 (27%)
Winter	1234 (22%)
Ethnicity	
Caucasian	4355 (79%)
African/American	402 (7%)
South East Asian	195 (4%)
North East Asian	137 (2%)
Other/Mixed	406 (7%)
Age (years)	9.79 (0.35)
Height (cm)	141.52 (6.60)
FEV ₁ (z-score)	0.16 (0.98)
FVC (z-score)	0.20 (0.94)
FEV ₁ /FVC (z-score)	-0.10 (0.96)
FEF _{25-75%} (z-score)	0.45 (1.09)
Preschool wheezing	1865 (37%)
School asthma	268 (6%)

469 *Values are mean (SD) for continuous variables and N (%) for categorical variables.
 470 Abbreviations: BMI: body mass index; FVC: forced vital capacity; FEV₁: forced expiratory volume in
 471 1s; FEF_{25-75%}: mid expiratory flow; SD: standard deviation.

472 **Table 3.** Associations of maternal exposure during pregnancy to the urban
 473 environment in clusters and lung function, preschool wheezing, and asthma in
 474 school-age children.
 475

	Maternal exposure to clusters of urban environment		
	Cluster 1 (n=1,598) ^a	Cluster 2 (n=2,835) ^a	Cluster 3 (n=1,191) ^a
		Estimate (95%CI)	Estimate (95%CI)
Lung function (z-score change)	<i>Reference</i>		
FEV ₁		-0.02 (-0.08, 0.05)	-0.03 (-0.11, 0.05)
FVC		-0.01 (-0.07, 0.05)	-0.02 (-0.09, 0.06)
FEV ₁ /FVC		0.00 (-0.06, 0.06)	-0.03 (-0.11, 0.05)
FEF _{25-75%}		-0.02 (-0.09, 0.05)	-0.08 (-0.17, 0.00)
Wheezing and asthma (OR)	<i>Reference</i>		
Preschool wheezing		1.13 (0.98, 1.29)	1.21 (1.03, 1.43)
School asthma		1.22 (0.91, 1.65)	1.02 (0.70, 1.48)

476
 477 ^a Cluster 1 (reference) identified mothers during pregnancy exposed to lower levels of air pollution,
 478 road traffic noise, traffic, and urbanisation, in terms of population density, building density, and
 479 walkability, and to higher levels of green and blue spaces, cluster 2 those exposed to lower levels of
 480 air pollutants and noise, higher distance to natural spaces, more densely population and built areas,
 481 and less diversity in land use, and cluster 3 those exposed to higher air pollution and noise, and lived
 482 in more walkable areas, with lower exposure to green and blue spaces. Lung function models were
 483 adjusted for maternal education, pre-pregnancy BMI, age, smoking during pregnancy, history of
 484 asthma or atopy, and child's ethnicity and season of birth. Preschool wheezing and school asthma
 485 models were additionally adjusted for child's sex. Abbreviations: FEV₁: forced expiratory volume in 1s;
 486 FVC: forced vital capacity; FEF_{25-75%}: mid expiratory flow; OR: odds ratio; CI: confidence interval.
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Figure 1. Description of the clusters of maternal exposure during pregnancy to the urban exposures.

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Bars represent the level of exposure of each urban exposure in the cluster compared to the mean level of exposure in the overall population (mean=0).

501 **REFERENCES**

- 502 1. Melén E, Guerra S. Recent advances in understanding lung function development.
503 F1000Research. 2017;6(726).
- 504 2. Barker DJP. The origins of the developmental origins theory. In: Journal of Internal
505 Medicine. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd; 2007. p. 412–7.
- 506 3. Miller MD, Marty MA. Impact of environmental chemicals on lung development. Vol.
507 118, Environmental Health Perspectives. National Institute of Environmental Health
508 Sciences; 2010. p. 1155–64.
- 509 4. Garcia E, Rice MB, Gold DR. Air pollution and lung function in children. J Allergy Clin
510 Immunol. 2021 Jul 1;148(1):1–14.
- 511 5. Khreis H, Kelly C, Tate J, Parslow R, Lucas K, Nieuwenhuijsen M. Exposure to traffic-
512 related air pollution and risk of development of childhood asthma: A systematic review
513 and meta-analysis. Vol. 100, Environment International. Pergamon; 2017. p. 1–31.
- 514 6. Gehring U, Wijga AH, Koppelman GH, Vonk JM, Smit HA, Brunekreef B. Air pollution
515 and the development of asthma from birth until young adulthood. Eur Respir J.
516 2020;56(1).
- 517 7. Fuertes E, Sunyer J, Gehring U, Porta D, Forastiere F, Cesaroni G, et al. Associations
518 between air pollution and pediatric eczema, rhinoconjunctivitis and asthma: A meta-
519 analysis of European birth cohorts. Environ Int. 2020 Mar 1;136.
- 520 8. Orellano P, Quaranta N, Reynoso J, Balbi B, Vasquez J. Effect of outdoor air pollution
521 on asthma exacerbations in children and adults: Systematic review and multilevel
522 meta-analysis. PLoS One. 2017;12(3):e0174050.
- 523 9. Mortimer K, Neugebauer R, Lurmann F, Alcorn S, Balmes J, Tager I. Air pollution and
524 pulmonary function in asthmatic children effects of prenatal and lifetime exposures.
525 Epidemiology. 2008 Jul;19(4):550–7.
- 526 10. Jedrychowski WA, Perera FP, Mauger U, Mroz E, Klimaszewska-Rembiasz M, Flak
527 E, et al. Effect of prenatal exposure to fine particulate matter on ventilatory lung
528 function of preschool children of non-smoking mothers. Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol.

- 529 2010;24(5):492–501.
- 530 11. Morales E, Garcia-Esteban R, Asensio De La Cruz O, Basterrechea M, Lertxundi A,
531 Martinez López De Dicastillo MD, et al. Intrauterine and early postnatal exposure to
532 outdoor air pollution and lung function at preschool age. *Thorax*. 2015;70:64–73.
- 533 12. Lee AG, Le Grand B, Hsu HHL, Chiu YHM, Brennan KJ, Bose S, et al. Prenatal fine
534 particulate exposure associated with reduced childhood lung function and nasal
535 epithelia GSTP1 hypermethylation: Sex-specific effects. *Respir Res*. 2018 Apr
536 27;19(1).
- 537 13. Bougas N, Rancièrè F, Beydon N, Viola M, Perrot X, Gabet S, et al. Traffic-related air
538 pollution, lung function, and host vulnerability new insights from the Paris birth cohort.
539 Vol. 15, *Annals of the American Thoracic Society*. American Thoracic Society; 2018. p.
540 599–607.
- 541 14. Cai Y, Hansell AL, Granell R, Blangiardo M, Zottoli M, Fecht D, et al. Prenatal, early-
542 life, and childhood exposure to air pollution and lung function: The ALSPAC cohort.
543 *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2020 Jul 1;202(1):112–23.
- 544 15. Hehua Z, Qing C, Shanyan G, Qijun W, Yuhong Z. The impact of prenatal exposure to
545 air pollution on childhood wheezing and asthma: A systematic review. Vol. 159,
546 *Environmental Research*. Academic Press Inc.; 2017. p. 519–30.
- 547 16. Lavigne É, Bélaïr MA, Duque DR, Do MT, Stieb DM, Hystad P, et al. Effect
548 modification of perinatal exposure to air pollution and childhood asthma incidence. *Eur*
549 *Respir J*. 2018 Mar 1;51(3):1701884.
- 550 17. Lee A, Leon Hsu HH, Mathilda Chiu YH, Bose S, Rosa MJ, Kloog I, et al. Prenatal fine
551 particulate exposure and early childhood asthma: Effect of maternal stress and fetal
552 sex. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*. 2018 May 1;141(5):1880–6.
- 553 18. Sbihi H, Koehoorn M, Tamburic L, Brauer M. Asthma trajectories in a population-
554 based birth cohort impacts of air pollution and greenness. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*.
555 2017 Mar 1;195(5):607–13.
- 556 19. Fuertes E, Bracher J, Flexeder C, Markevych I, Klümper C, Hoffmann B, et al. Long-

- 557 term air pollution exposure and lung function in 15 year-old adolescents living in an
558 urban and rural area in Germany: The GINIplus and LISAPLUS cohorts. *Int J Hyg*
559 *Environ Health*. 2015 Oct 1;218(7):656–65.
- 560 20. Gehring U, Gruzieva O, Agius RM, Beelen R, Custovic A, Cyrus J, et al. Air pollution
561 exposure and lung function in children: The ESCAPE project. *Environ Health*
562 *Perspect*. 2013;121(11–12):1357–64.
- 563 21. Agier L, Basagaña X, Maitre L, Granum B, Bird PK, Casas M, et al. Early-life
564 exposome and lung function in children in Europe: an analysis of data from the
565 longitudinal, population-based HELIX cohort. *Lancet Planet Heal*. 2019;3(2):e81–92.
- 566 22. Wallas AE, Eriksson C, Ögren M, Pyko A, Sjöström M, Melén E, et al. Noise exposure
567 and childhood asthma up to adolescence. *Environ Res*. 2020 Jun 1;185:109404.
- 568 23. Fuertes E, Markevych I, Thomas R, Boyd A, Granell R, Mahmoud O, et al. Residential
569 greenspace and lung function up to 24 years of age: The ALSPAC birth cohort.
570 *Environ Int*. 2020 Jul 1;140.
- 571 24. Parmes E, Pesce G, Sabel CE, Baldacci S, Bono R, Brescianini S, et al. Influence of
572 residential land cover on childhood allergic and respiratory symptoms and diseases:
573 Evidence from 9 European cohorts. *Environ Res*. 2020 Apr 1;183:108953.
- 574 25. Gascon M, Vrijheid M, Nieuwenhuijsen MJ. The Built Environment and Child Health:
575 An Overview of Current Evidence. *Curr Environ Heal reports*. 2016;3(3):250–7.
- 576 26. United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs PD. The World's Cities in
577 2018 - Data Booklet. 2018.
- 578 27. Rao M, Prasad S, Adshead F, Tissera H. The built environment and health. *Lancet*.
579 2007 Sep 29;370(9593):1111–3.
- 580 28. Jaddoe VWV, Van Duijn CM, Franco OH, Van Der Heijden AJ, Van Ilzendoorn MH,
581 De Jongste JC, et al. The generation r study: Design and cohort update 2012. *Eur J*
582 *Epidemiol*. 2012 Sep;27(9):739–56.
- 583 29. Miller MR, Hankinson J, Brusasco V, Burgos F, Casaburi R, Coates A, et al.
584 Standardisation of spirometry. *Eur Respir J*. 2005 Aug 1;26(2):319–38.

- 585 30. Quanjer PH, Stanojevic S, Cole TJ, Baur X, Hall GL, Culver BH, et al. Multi-ethnic
586 reference values for spirometry for the 3-95-yr age range: The global lung function
587 2012 equations. *Eur Respir J*. 2012 Dec 1;40(6):1324–43.
- 588 31. Stanojevic S, Quanjer P, Miller MR, Stocks J. The Global Lung Function Initiative:
589 dispelling some myths of lung function test interpretation. *Breathe*. 2013;9(463).
- 590 32. Asher MI, Keil U, Anderson HR, Beasley R, Crane J, Martinez F, et al. International
591 study of asthma and allergies in childhood (ISAAC): Rationale and methods. In:
592 *European Respiratory Journal*. 1995. p. 483–91.
- 593 33. White IR, Royston P, Wood AM. Multiple imputation using chained equations: Issues
594 and guidance for practice. *Stat Med*. 2011;30(4):377–99.
- 595 34. Li MX, Yeung JMY, Cherny SS, Sham PC. Evaluating the effective numbers of
596 independent tests and significant p-value thresholds in commercial genotyping arrays
597 and public imputation reference datasets. *Hum Genet*. 2012 May 6;131(5):747–56.
- 598 35. Chen G, Zhou H, He G, Zhu S, Sun X, Ye Y, et al. Effect of early-life exposure to PM 2
599 .5 on childhood asthma/wheezing: a birth cohort study. *Pediatr Allergy Immunol*. 2022
600 Jun 1;33(6).
- 601 36. Marseglia GL, Cirillo I, Vizzaccaro A, Klersy C, Tosca MA, Rosa M La, et al. Role of
602 forced expiratory flow at 25-75% as an early marker of small airways impairment in
603 subjects with allergic rhinitis. Vol. 28, *Allergy and Asthma Proceedings*. Allergy
604 *Asthma Proc*; 2007. p. 74–8.
- 605 37. Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. Inhabitants per municipality [Internet]. 2023 [cited
606 2023 Dec 2]. Available from: [https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/visualisaties/dashboard-](https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/visualisaties/dashboard-bevolking/regionaal/inwoners)
607 [bevolking/regionaal/inwoners](https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/visualisaties/dashboard-bevolking/regionaal/inwoners)
- 608 38. Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. Where can we ride our bikes? - The Netherlands
609 in numbers [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2023 Dec 2]. Available from:
610 [https://longreads.cbs.nl/the-netherlands-in-numbers-2023/where-can-we-ride-our-](https://longreads.cbs.nl/the-netherlands-in-numbers-2023/where-can-we-ride-our-bikes/)
611 [bikes/](https://longreads.cbs.nl/the-netherlands-in-numbers-2023/where-can-we-ride-our-bikes/)
- 612 39. Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. New socioeconomic status scores for districts and

- 613 neighbourhoods [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2023 Dec 2]. Available from:
614 [https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb/our-services/customised-services-microdata/microdata-](https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb/our-services/customised-services-microdata/microdata-conducting-your-own-research/microdatabijeenkomsten/bijeenkomsten/new-socioeconomic-status-scores-for-districts-and-neighbourhoods)
615 [conducting-your-own-research/microdatabijeenkomsten/bijeenkomsten/new-](https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb/our-services/customised-services-microdata/microdata-conducting-your-own-research/microdatabijeenkomsten/bijeenkomsten/new-socioeconomic-status-scores-for-districts-and-neighbourhoods)
616 [socioeconomic-status-scores-for-districts-and-neighbourhoods](https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb/our-services/customised-services-microdata/microdata-conducting-your-own-research/microdatabijeenkomsten/bijeenkomsten/new-socioeconomic-status-scores-for-districts-and-neighbourhoods)
- 617 40. Kivimäki M, Batty GD, Pentti J, Shipley MJ, Sipilä PN, Nyberg ST, et al. Association
618 between socioeconomic status and the development of mental and physical health
619 conditions in adulthood: a multi-cohort study. *Lancet Public Heal*. 2020 Mar
620 1;5(3):e140–9.
- 621 41. Sum KK, Tint MT, Aguilera R, Dickens BSL, Choo S, Ang LT, et al. The
622 socioeconomic landscape of the exposome during pregnancy. *Environ Int*. 2022 May
623 1;163:107205.
- 624 42. Hajat A, Hsia C, O'Neill MS. Socioeconomic Disparities and Air Pollution Exposure: a
625 Global Review. Vol. 2, Current environmental health reports. Springer; 2015. p. 440–
626 50.
- 627 43. Bové H, Bongaerts E, Slenders E, Bijmens EM, Saenen ND, Gyselaers W, et al.
628 Ambient black carbon particles reach the fetal side of human placenta. *Nat Commun*.
629 2019 Dec 1;10(1):1–7.
- 630 44. Thurston GD, Balmes JR, Garcia E, Gilliland FD, Rice MB, Schikowski T, et al.
631 Outdoor air pollution and new-onset airway disease: An official american thoracic
632 society workshop report. In: *Annals of the American Thoracic Society*. American
633 Thoracic Society; 2020. p. 387–98.
- 634 45. Thomson EM. Air Pollution, Stress, and Allostatic Load: Linking Systemic and Central
635 Nervous System Impacts. *J Alzheimers Dis*. 2019;69(3):597–614.
- 636 46. Beamer PI, Furlong M, Lothrop N, Guerra S, Billheimer D, Stern DA, et al. CC16
637 Levels into Adult Life Are Associated with Nitrogen Dioxide Exposure at Birth. *Am J*
638 *Respir Crit Care Med*. 2019 Sep 1;200(5):600–7.
- 639 47. Stapleton A, Casas M, García J, García R, Sunyer J, Guerra S, et al. Associations
640 between pre- and postnatal exposure to air pollution and lung health in children and

- 641 assessment of CC16 as a potential mediator. *Environ Res.* 2022 Mar 1;204:111900.
- 642 48. Recio A, Linares C, Banegas JR, Díaz J. Road traffic noise effects on cardiovascular,
643 respiratory, and metabolic health: An integrative model of biological mechanisms. Vol.
644 146, *Environmental Research*. Academic Press Inc.; 2016. p. 359–70.
- 645 49. Guxens M, Sonnenschein-Van Der Voort AMM, Tiemeier H, Hofman A, Sunyer J, De
646 Jongste JC, et al. Parental psychological distress during pregnancy and wheezing in
647 preschool children: The Generation R Study. *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 2014;133(1).
- 648 50. Van Meel ER, Saharan G, Jaddoe VWV, De Jongste JC, Reiss IKM, Tiemeier H, et al.
649 Parental psychological distress during pregnancy and the risk of childhood lower lung
650 function and asthma: A population-based prospective cohort study. *Thorax.* 2020 Dec
651 1;75(12):1074–81.
- 652 51. Schmidt FP, Basner M, Kröger G, Weck S, Schnorbus B, Muttray A, et al. Effect of
653 nighttime aircraft noise exposure on endothelial function and stress hormone release
654 in healthy adults. *Eur Heart J.* 2013 Dec 1;34(45):3508–14.
- 655 52. Heo S, Bell ML. The influence of green space on the short-term effects of particulate
656 matter on hospitalization in the U.S. for 2000–2013. *Environ Res.* 2019 Jul 1;174:61–
657 8.
- 658 53. Ruokolainen L, Von Hertzen L, Fyhrquist N, Laatikainen T, Lehtomäki J, Auvinen P, et
659 al. Green areas around homes reduce atopic sensitization in children. *Allergy.* 2015
660 Feb 1;70(2):195–202.
- 661 54. van den Bosch M, Ode Sang. Urban natural environments as nature-based solutions
662 for improved public health – A systematic review of reviews. *Environ Res.*
663 2017;158:373–84.
- 664 55. Prescott SL. A butterfly flaps its wings: Extinction of biological experience and the
665 origins of allergy. Vol. 125, *Annals of Allergy, Asthma and Immunology*. American
666 College of Allergy, Asthma and Immunology; 2020. p. 528–34.
- 667 56. Nieuwenhuijsen MJ. Urban and transport planning, environmental exposures and
668 health-new concepts, methods and tools to improve health in cities. Vol. 15,

669 Environmental Health: A Global Access Science Source. BioMed Central Ltd.; 2016. p.
670 161–71.

671 57. Santos S, Maitre L, Warembourg C, Agier L, Richiardi L, Basagaña X, et al. Applying
672 the exposome concept in birth cohort research: a review of statistical approaches. *Eur*
673 *J Epidemiol.* 2020 Mar 1;35(3):193–204.

674 58. Warembourg C, Anguita-Ruiz A, Siroux V, Slama R, Vrijheid M, Richiardi L, et al.
675 Statistical Approaches to Study Exposome-Health Associations in the Context of
676 Repeated Exposure Data: A Simulation Study. *Environ Sci Technol.* 2023 Oct
677 31;57(43):16232–43.

678